

TALENTED YOUTH ARE THE BASIS OF SOCIETY'S DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: This article talks about the specific psychological aspects of talented young people. At the same time, information was also given about the opportunities for talented young people in our country.

Keywords: spirituality, talent, youth policy, art, intellectual talent, culture, potential.

The final goal of the spiritual and educational reforms, which are rapidly continuing in the new Uzbekistan, is to achieve new results in terms of pleasing the people and ensuring the viability of national values. Proper education of young people in all aspects is one of the urgent tasks.

President Sh. Mirziyoyev: “Spirituality for us is mutual trust, respect and attention between people, noble aspirations to jointly build the future of the nation and the state, and a complex of exemplary qualities. In other words, it is the foundation that determines the content and quality of all political and social relations[1: 267] – he emphasized.

Young people with high morale are also needed for the development of the society. The development of the society also depends on the creative works of intellectual, potential and talented young people. Therefore, a talented person is a solid foundation of the society. People rich in creative ideas and perfect creativity have always been considered a pillar of society. Therefore, in the science of psychology, great attention is paid to the individual typological characteristics of talented young people.

First of all, talent is a combination of psychological abilities, which is a force that allows individuals to successfully perform certain activities.

During the research, we pay attention to the individual typological characteristics of talented young people, and in psychology we distinguish talented and capable young people according to their typological characteristics. Talented young people have intellectual talent, are familiar with music, dance, academic, social (engagement with others), do sports, and are not alien to such qualities as

strong oratory and literary eloquence. Genius activities are usually about generating new ideas as well as using very simple approaches to solving problems [2: 1304].

In recent years, great work has been done by the Ministry of Culture to identify creative and talented young people. Today, a total of 367 educational institutions are operating in the system of the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In particular, there are 325 children's music and art schools, 29 specialized art and culture schools and boarding schools, 2 colleges, 5 higher education institutions and their 4 branches, and 2 training centers. More than 20,000 professors and teachers are teaching 111,421 students in these educational institutions.

In particular, there are 90 thousand 85 children in music and art schools, 9 thousand 967 in secondary special educational institutions, and 11 thousand 371 in higher educational institutions. In particular: a number of new higher educational institutions, such as the Uzbek National Institute of Music Art named after Yunus Rajabi, the National Institute of Pop Art named after Botir Zakirov, were launched in Tashkent, and their number increased from 5 to 10. This, in turn, further strengthened the system of preservation and development of unique examples of classical and folk art, specific performance schools and traditions. It was an important practical step towards showing the unique talent of our creative youth not only in our republic, but also on a global scale.

The number of children's music and art schools in the regions increased by 19, from 305 to 324. Scientific research institutions and training centers increased by 2, from 1 to 3 [3: 1].

Regarding such reforms, President Sh. Mirziyoyev said: "You all understand well that if the body of society's life is the economy, then its soul and spirit is spirituality. We rely on these two strong pillars in the establishment of New Uzbekistan, that is, a strong economy based on market principles and a strong spirituality based on the rich heritage of our ancestors, national and universal values"[4: 4].

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